

METHOD OF DETERMINATION OF PROPERTIES OF BIOCHEMICAL COMPOUNDS

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Abstract. *I had the honor to work as a reflexologist in the city of Krasnodar, Russian Federation. During the period from May 2016 to May 2022, I conducted research in the clinic of Academician Malanyin Igor Valentinovich on diagnostics and treatment with the use of the energetic approach. energetic approach, namely Typology (of temperament, nature, mizaj).*

But modern medicine does not take into account the type of organ, disease, drugs on the system of energy (mizaj according to Avicenna), which was studied in limited concepts such as the works of Pavlov I.V. about temperament. In this work I scientifically substantiate Mizage. The theory of temperament and nature do not fully cover the concepts of Avicenna Mizage. The relevance of the concept of Mizaj on the scientific basis, will give us - Doctors of the Modern World to understand the roots of centuries-old folk medicine and "connect" us with Avicenna!

Keywords: *type, temperament, mizage. A way to determine the types of photon, light, color, ultraviolet, visible, infrared spectra and biochemical compounds. Diagnosis and treatment by type.*

Introduction: Let's start from breaking down what "properties" mean. "Property" includes the concepts of type, nature, energy, and mizaj (the term *mizaj* will further be replaced by the term *type* in accordance with Avicenna's concept (1)). The type is the foundation of all principles and has its own energy. All organs, pathological factors, medicinal substances, and compounds can be classified into four types: cold, moisture, dryness, and heat, depending on their geographical location (2).

The energy of a photon, which is the energy of a quantum, is considered the criterion for dividing colors by type, functional organs, and substance types. Light emission occurs when an atom transitions from a stationary state with higher energy to a stationary state with lower energy:

- In the optical range, the energy of the photon follows this order: $E_1 > E_2 > E_3 > E_4$.
- In the ultraviolet and infrared ranges, the energy of the photon follows this order: $E_1 > E_2 = E_3 > E_4$.

When a photon is absorbed by a substance, it can excite the molecule, and the electron can jump from one orbital to another. Each photon transition is associated with a specific nature, properties, and Type (13). All substances, including medicines, phytotherapeutic and homeopathic preparations, as well as the food and liquids we consume, have their own spectral color (see photo 1).

1. We determine the color type according to Teslin E.V.'s teachings and code the color type using the R.G.B system (see photo 3). In order to achieve noticeable results, it is necessary to represent colors in symbolic forms (fire, water, wood, etc.) - Teslin E.V. 2010 (12). Type 1, Organs Brain and Kidneys – water, cold. Type 2, Neuro-endocrine organs – air, moisture. Type 3, Organs Liver and Pancreas – earth, dryness. Type 4, Organs Heart and Lungs – fire, heat.

Organotrophic effect on the projection skin zone of the affected organ causes a reason ant response of the organ through sensory pathways from the spinal cord segments. Impulses are switched twice: at the spinal cord segment level and then through ascending pathways to the brainstem nuclei and subcortical structures (thalamus, hypothalamus, neurohypophysis), which promotes the restoration of segmental and central regulation of the functions of the affected organ (11.1-1-0-68).

In this case, the colors in the RGB system are divided into two groups by codes:

- Group 1 includes all colors from 0.0.0 to 127.127.127. For convenience, this group is assigned the conditional designation "0".
- Group 2 includes all colors from 128.128.128 to 255.255.255. This group is assigned the conditional designation "1" (25, 26, and see Table No. 1, see Photo No. 3).

The importance of the issue lies in revealing the connection between the type of photon energy (color).

1. In the UV spectrum, the type of photon energy (18) plays an important role in determining the characteristics of biochemical compounds, drugs, proteins, genes, DNA, RNA, peptides, molecules, microorganisms, and pathological substances.
2. In the IR spectrum, the type of photon energy (color) plays an important role in determining the characteristics of smell, taste, and the type of substances, including drugs and biochemical compounds (6, 7).
3. In the optical (visible) spectrum, the type of photon energy (color) plays an important role in determining the type of organ, disease, and substance, including drugs and biochemical compounds (see Table N. 2).

The reference for determining the visible spectrum is based on the hydrogen electron transitions: $H. > H. > H. > H.$

The reference for determining the ultraviolet (UV) and infrared (IR) spectra is based on electron transitions between energy levels: $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (see Table No. 1, 3).

Each photon transition corresponds to properties and type – mizaj.
2. Determining the type of substances: I placed the winds (moisture) after the cold, between the winds and heat (fire) lies the earth (dryness). Basis: “We sent the winds that fertilize...” (1). “Heat is nourished by moisture” $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ nourishes $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and life is born from warmth.” Avicenna (2, 1, II, 13).

The rules for determining the type of visible color and optical spectrum of a substance are based on the electron jumps in the hydrogen atom across energy levels of Balmer: $H. > H. > H. > H.$ (see Photo 1, see Table No. 2).

H. - nature type – 1 cold, 410,2 nm – 434,1nm (26, 28 and figure № 2,3).

H. - nature type – 2 humidity, 434,1 nm – 486,1 nm

H. - nature type – 3 dryness 486,1 nm – 656,3 nm

H. - nature type – 4 heat 656,3 nm – 780 nm

Here is the translation of your text into English:

In the ultraviolet and infrared color ranges, based on the rules of electron transitions between energy levels:

$\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (see photos 2, 3, see Table N. 3).

3. Determining the type of functional organ and the type of disease, taking into account the organotropic nature of color and substance types.

Type is the manifestation of energy in the form of quanta that participate in all reactions of the body, microorganisms, cells, proteins, peptides, DNA, RNA, amino acids, receptors, etc.

- **Type 1:** Organs: Brain and kidneys are associated with water, cold (20). Biochemical bonds with hydrogen: -OH, -CH, -NH (7, 12, 13 - 23).
- **Type 2:** Neuro-endocrine organs are associated with air, moisture. Biochemical bonds may include double bonds: C = C, C = N, C = O, C = S.
- **Type 3:** Organs: Liver and pancreas. Biochemical bonds may vary, and one of them is a single bond: C -Hal, C = F, C = Cl, C = Br, C = O = C.
- **Type 4:** Heart and lungs. Biochemical bonds: Triple bonds and cumulenes: C. C -, -C. N-, C = C = C.

According to Avicenna's teachings, organ types are also distributed in the above-mentioned order. The hottest energy in the body was considered to be psychic energy, followed by the following in decreasing order: heart, semen, blood, liver, muscles, spleen, kidneys, arteries, intestines, skin, lymph, hair, bones, cartilage, joints, tendons, membranes, mucous membranes, internal fat, and fat (15). Based on this sequence of organ temperature in the body, we can distinguish four types of functional organs:

1. Heart, blood - Type 4
2. Liver, muscles - Type 3
3. Spleen - Type 2
4. Kidneys - Type 1 (see photos 4, 5).

Determining the type of disease. Disruptions in the properties of energy can be viewed as types of diseases. The first type of disorders relates to diseases associated with the liquid environment of "Water" organs, such as juices, blood plasma, lymph, cerebrospinal fluid, transudates, exudates, and cytoplasm. This type of disorder is usually associated with the blue color. These are diseases of functional organs: brain and kidneys. The second type of disorders, associated with the properties of "Air," includes various diseases related to morphofunctional movements, expansions, and contractions of blood and lymphatic vessels, bile and pancreatic ducts, exocrine ducts, as well as disturbances in nerve conduction from the central nervous system (CNS) and autonomic nervous system (ANS), nerve cells, and receptors in tissues. This type of disorder is usually associated with the yellow color.

These types of diseases include disorders of the neuroendocrine systems.

The third type of disorder, associated with the properties of "Earth," includes diseases that affect solid, supportive, insulating, and nourishing environments of cells, tissues, and organs. The presence of "Earth" properties in existing substances contributes to their cohesion and strength, maintaining outlines and shape. This type of property is associated with the green color. Functional organs such as the liver and pancreas may be associated with this type of disorder. The fourth type of disorder, associated with the properties of "Fire," includes diseases related to metabolic processes, metabolism, perception, intellect, thermoregulation, and the body's enzyme system. The characteristic signs of this type of disorder may be associated with the red color. Functional organs, such as the heart and lungs, may be linked to this type of disorder (17, see Photo 4, and see Table N. 1).

5. **Treatment Rules.**

The diagnosis and treatment of diseases are based on the use of various instrumental methods depending on the specific pathology, as each organ may be susceptible to different types of pathologies, requiring individualized therapy (8. 1-1248, 2-41).

The effectiveness of drugs depends on the physical, biological, and chemical properties of the entire molecule, which in in vivo conditions may differ from the predicted properties, such as in in vitro experiments, modeling, or other predictive methods (19. 83-98, 134-138, 378-380). Using the terminology of pharmacodynamics, it can be noted that during biotransformation, absorption, accumulation, and elimination in the body (in vivo), energy is released and accounted for.

Pharmacodynamics typically does not consider the spectral (type) quality of medicinal substances.

The principle of therapy, described by Avicenna:

According to this principle, the chosen type of substance should correspond to the type of organ or system and counteract the type of disease (pathological factor). It is important that such therapy does not disrupt the processes of pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics.

"Indeed, when the quality of the disease is understood, one must choose a medicine with the counteracting quality, for disease is treated by opposition, and health is preserved by cooperation" (3. 379, see Photo No. 6).

A medicine with cold properties (Type 1) may be used to counteract a disease type characterized by heat symptoms (Type 4).

The nature (type - mizaj) of fruits, vegetables, and a number of other products can be complex, meaning it consists of a combination of different properties: hot and dry, hot and moist, cold and dry, as well as cold and moist (4). The fact is that the beginning of life—the heart and pneuma—are both very hot and prone to excess [heat]. Life arises from heat, and growth from moisture; furthermore, heat arises from moisture and is nourished by moisture (4). Or – "We sent the winds, fertilizing..." (1).

Health can be supported by the proper selection of medicinal substances that correspond to the type of disease and the functional state of the organ (3. 379, 5, and see Photo No. 6).

Avicenna believed that each person has a certain predominant nature, and when treating, this individuality should be taken into account (15).

Combination therapy, considering spectral color, may lead to new technical results and improve treatment efficiency. In accordance with mizaj (hot, cold, dry, or moist), medicines manifested corresponding effects such as warming, cooling, drying, or moistening (20).

The opposite of a type: Cold - Heat, Moisture - Dryness.

The technical result of combination therapy, taking into account spectral color, is the enhancement of treatment effectiveness, which may lead to new achievements and innovations in the fields of chemistry and medicine (see therapy principle). The novelty lies in selecting medicinal preparations according to the color spectrum. Additionally, this improves the quality of treatment.

Examples: Type of medicinal substances (9, 10, 16). Hormonal preparations.

- Dexamethasone – 1680 cm^{-1} * Type 3
- Prednisolone – 1670 cm^{-1} ** Type 3
- Noradrenaline – 1280 cm^{-1} * Type 4
- Testosterone Propionate – 1280 cm^{-1} * Type 4
- Adrenaline, hormone O–H stretch $3650\text{-}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, Type 1

- Oxytocin neuropeptide and hormone O–H stretch 3650-3200 cm^{-1} , Type 1 • Type 1
- Progesterone C–H stretch 3000-2840 cm^{-1} , Type 1
- Thyroxine-T4 prohormone to triiodothyronine O–H stretch 3650-3200 cm^{-1} , Type 1

- Corticosteroids 1500 cm^{-1} Type 4

Antibiotics:

- Benzylpenicillin Potassium – 1610 cm^{-1} * Type 3
- Ampicillin Sodium – 1600 cm^{-1} * Type 3
- Cefotaxime Sodium – 1510 cm^{-1} * Type 3
- Sulbactam – 3000-2840 cm^{-1} , Type 1
- Isoniazid – 1690 cm^{-1} ** Type 2

Vitamins:

- Ergocalciferol – 2990 cm^{-1} * Type 1

Tocopherol Acetate – Tocopherol acetate 2980 cm^{-1} type 1

Various medicinal preparations (16, 17):

1. Wormwood (*Artemisia absinthium*) herb tincture in UV light 365 nm type 4.
2. Hawthorn fruit tincture. In UV light 365 nm type 4.
3. Peppermint leaf tincture *Menthae piperitae folii tinctura*. Transparent liquid from light green to dark green color type 2.
4. Human immunoglobulin against COVID-19, intravenous solution. Description: Transparent or slightly opalescent, colorless or light yellow solution type 3.

Results and Discussion. Interestingly, in the clinic of Academician I.S. Malanin, analyses were conducted on the impact of colors on the body of 45 patients with various pathologies. The study used different methods considering the type of colors of medicines, physiotherapeutic laser colors, reflexotherapy, phytotherapy, homeopathy, and dietotherapy.

The patients were divided into two groups: The first, control group, consisted of 21 patients. In this group, treatment was carried out without considering the type of organ, disease, and medicinal substances.

The second, examined group, consisted of 24 patients. During the treatment, the type of organ, disease, and medicinal substances were taken into account. The treatment course for both groups of patients consisted of 7 to 12 sessions. Both groups underwent conservative treatments (pharmacotherapy, phytotherapy, homeopathy, dietotherapy, laser therapy, and acupuncture).

Determining the dominant type in a substance:

1. If the substance contains all types, the substance of the primary type is considered the first type.
2. If a substance contains more of one type than the others, that type is considered the primary type.
3. The primary type is considered the one with the active bond of higher energy and shorter wavelength than the rest.

Conclusions. The study concluded that treatment considering the type of organ, disease, and medicinal substances has a more pathophysiological impact and leads to more stable positive effects, such as improvement in well-being and recovery.

TYPES OF MEDICINAL SUBSTANCES.

Ampicillin Sodium 1600 cm-1* type 3

Tocopherol 2990 cm-1 type 1

Progesterone 1680 cm-1 type 3

Diclofenac Sodium 1600 cm-1 type 3

Furosemide 1140 cm-1 type 4

Source(27) <https://mydocx.ru/4-67730.html>

It was also noted that the number of repeat visits with corresponding complaints decreased, indicating more prolonged and stable improvement of patients' conditions. The effectiveness of treatment considering the type (Mizaj) ranged from 4% to 16%. This means that between 4% and 16% of patients achieved positive results from this type of treatment (see Table No. 4). Chromotherapy, laser therapy, phytotherapy, homeopathy, reflexotherapy, and dietotherapy are generally considered more natural and less harmful methods of treatment for the body.

PHOTOS, DIAGRAMS, AND TABLES. Wavelengths & Photons

Particles of light, called photons, each have a wavelength.

Photo N. 1. The Four Main Colors of Photon.
Source: (24) <https://slideplayer.com/slide/6014763/>.

Photo N. 2. Electronic Transitions.
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Photo 3. Color Type according to the R.G.B System (25, 26).

Photo N. 4. Characteristic Vibrations. (21).

wikipedia.org/wiki/File:IR-spectroscopy-sample.svg

Photo N. 5. Type of photon energy of biogenic substances according to the IR spectrum.

Source of the photo from. (22) <https://www.mdpi.com/1422-0067/22/3/1206/xml>

Photo - N. 6. Relationships of the 4 Mizaj

1. **Water** - Brain, Lymph, Cold

2. **Air** - Heart, Blood, Humidity

3. **Earth** - Spleen, Black bile, Dryness

4. **Fire** - Liver, Bile, Heat

A.

Cold and Humid

Warm and Humid

Cold and Dry

Warm and Dry

E

Deficiency of Cold

F

Deficiency of Humidity

G

Deficiency of Dryness

H

Deficiency of Heat

Heat Excess of Dryness Excess of Humidity Excess of Cold

TABLES Table N. 1. Type of Functional Organ

1	1.0.1.	0.1.1.	0.1.0.	1.1.0.	1.1.0.	1.0.0.
2	$\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$		$n \rightarrow \sigma^*$		$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ и $n \rightarrow \pi^*$
3	Water	Air		Earth		Fire
4	Cold	Humidity		Dryness		Heat
5	Brain, Kidneys	Neuroendocrine		Liver		Heart
6	type 1	type 2		type 3		type 4

Notes:

A. Rows horizontally:

1 - Color and RGB code.

2 - Energy transitions.

3 - Properties.

4 - Energy. 5 - Functional organ. 6 - Type. B. According to Avicenna, "Heat is nourished by moisture" - $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ nourishes $n \rightarrow \pi^*$.

Table N. 2. Types of optical radiation line width, compared with Fraunhofer lines.

Type

Source (23). Light, the visible spectrum; open-electronics.org.

Notes: The width of types is marked with Roman numerals.

Table No. 3. Correspondence between types of photon energy, color types, and Mizaj.

1	UV spectrum; type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type
2	100–150nm	150–200nm	200–300nm	300–350nm
3	IR spectrum: type 1	тип 2	тип 3	тип 4
4	$\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	$n \rightarrow \sigma^*$	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$
5	3200 cm ⁻¹ 2800cm ⁻¹	2100cm ⁻¹	1500 cm ⁻¹	400 cm ⁻¹
6	4000 cm ⁻¹ 3200cm ⁻¹	2300cm ⁻¹	1800 cm ⁻¹	1400 cm ⁻¹
7	Valence vibrations:	Valence vibrations:	Valence vibrations:	Valence vibrations:
8	M-H, XH C - H	A ≡ B, A=B=C	A = B	C - Hal
9	CONH	C = C	C = C	C - F
10	O - H		C = O	C - Cl
11	N - H	C = N N = C = O	C = N	C - Br
12	S - H	N = C = S	C = S	C-O-C
13	Vision spectrum: type 1	Type 2	type3	type 4
14	H _δ	H _γ	H _β	H _α
15	410,2 – 434,0 nm	434,1–486,0 nm	486,1-656,2nm	656,3-780 nm
16	E= 2,8 – 3,1eV	E= 2,6 – 2,8 eV	E= 1,9 – 2,6 eV	E= 1,6 – 1,9eV
17	Water	Air	Earth	Fire

Note to Table № 3. Row numbers:

1. Photon energy type (color), type of substance (medications, biochemical compounds) in the UV spectrum.

2. Type of photon energy (wavelength) in the UV spectrum.
3. Type of photon energy (color), type of smell and taste, type of substance (medications, biochemical compounds) in the IR spectrum.
4. Type of energy of electron jumps in the IR spectrum.
- 5,6. Type of photon energy (wavelength) in the IR spectrum.
- 7 – 12. Types of compound substances in the IR spectrum.
13. Type of photon energy (color), type of organ, disease, and substance (medications, biochemical compounds) in the optical (visible) spectrum.
14. Type of energy of electron jump – photon in the optical spectrum.
- 15,16. Type of photon energy (wavelength) in the optical (visible) spectrum.

In rows 1, 3, 13, the natural colors of photons by type are indicated.

In row 17: types of organ, disease, and substances.

Table No. 4: Effectiveness indicator of treatment by type (Mizaj).

№	Effect	Control Group			Experimental Group			Effectiveness
		Count	Count	Percentage	Count	Count	Percentage	
1	Analgesic	21	15	71,4%	24	21	87,5%	+ 16,1 %
2	Tonic	21	17	80,9%	24	22	91,6%	+10,7 %
3	Calming	21	20	95,2%	24	24	100 %	+ 4,8 %
4	Repeated visits per year	21	5	23,8%	24	2	8,33%	+ 15,47%

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